

Almost a Year with COVID-19: What is Ahead?

Aasim A. Azooz^{1*}

¹Former Professor of Applied Physics, Retired from Mosul University – Iraq

* Corresponding Author : aasimazooz1@yahoo.com

Abstract

The lessons learnt during the 2020 covid-19 pandemic are reviewed. Data on the pandemic spread and development are examined. In spite of spatial world variations in the pattern by which the pandemic developed from one world region to another, it seems that the overall world general pattern is of a simple type that can be empirically modelled with a single mathematical equations. This equation is capable of predicting the future behavior of the number of infections and deaths. Assuming no fully effective vaccine or treatment will be widely available within 2021, the model suggests that some type of leveling-off in the number of infections will start to take place by the middle of 2022.

Introduction

It is now clear that the whole world has been taken off guard by the COVID-19 pandemic. Even those who do not believe in conspiracy theory are completely surprised by the fact that all national security bodies in all world countries have failed to include such a scenario in their list of possible threats. The lack of such preparedness by all world countries became clear by the almost chaotic response of most countries to the pandemic. Even the world health organization (WHO) which is the world major body responsible for responding to such pandemic was characterized by inadequate preparedness to handle the situation in providing advice to the world. It took the WHO until March-11-2020 (That is more than two months after the start of the pandemic) to declare that COVID-19 is a global health crisis ^[1].

Empty handed from any means for combating the pandemic, the only available course of action at the disposal of all world countries was imposing social distancing measures. These amounted to almost complete shutdown of all industrial, economic and social activities. It was clear from the very beginning that such measures cannot be sustained for extended periods of time. Soon enough social distancing became a subject of criticism by many sectors of the community worldwide. The subject became even a political issue between competing factions in many countries. Sweden is one special case where no lockdown was imposed. Instead, Sweden followed the course of generating what is called Herd immunity ^[2]. Interestingly, the accumulated number of infections per one million of the population (IPM) on October 13, 2020 ^[3] is 9731 compared to Spain 19637 France 11383 and UK 9085. This may indicate that lockdown policies did not produce the desired control of the pandemic.

From geographical point of view, the pandemic is characterized by some interesting patterns. These patterns involve both the date of onset of the pandemic and the overall IPM. As far as the date of onset is concerned, some countries did not start to feel the burden of the pandemic until beginning of May 2020. Examples of such countries are India, Brazil, Argentina, South Africa and Bangladesh, The pandemic in most other countries became a fact of life as early as January or February 2020. This time lack may be attributed to weather related factors such as temperature, humidity and ultraviolet radiation. It can also be simply the result of failure in reporting early cases of infections. The same applies as far as the IPM metric is concerned. Here, Africa present a surprising situation with only 1964 infections per million of the population by October 13, 2020. The number is far

below the corresponding ones of 9086 for Europe, 24244 for North America, 2673 for Asia. However, data inaccuracies cannot be ruled out as one reason for such lower IPM value in Africa. In general, more developed countries tend to show higher IPM numbers compared to less developed ones.

There has always been concerns that a second wave of the pandemic may hit many countries as weather conditions move towards autumn and winter. Such effect even if applicable has been overshadowed by a second waves of the pandemic resulting from relaxing the social distancing measures in many countries. Clear shoot ups in infections curves show up at dates post easing such restrictions. Typical examples of such trends can be seen in figure (1) for the USA and Spain. Start of shoot ups in the number of infections is evident post day 150 from January 22. This corresponds to about mid-June. This is only few weeks after the US and Spain relaxed their lockdown measures to a significant degree. The shoot up in the number of infections is appears more pronounced when one plots the daily new infections as shown in figure (2). The same patterns is observed in the data for most other European countries including France, Germany, Italy, the UK ...etc.

It can thus be argued that any expected second wave assumed to be due to approach of Autumn and Winter seasons may have already been hidden within the sharp rises in infection caused by the relaxations of lockdown measures by most countries. Even so the situation with what effects weather conditions might have on the pandemic is still unclear ^[4-7].

Authorities in different parts of the world have been struggling to strike the correct balance between saving as many as possible numbers of lives through the imposition of social distancing measures on one hand, and trying to minimize the social and economic damages such measures create. Although most communities reluctantly accepted the stay home policies for the first two or three months, global resentments to such policies have become more widespread. The economic price of social distancing was huge enough resulting in huge losses of jobs, depressed national growth rates, and a worldwide recession ^[8,9]. Aviation sector is the most hit ^[10]. Restriction on religious gatherings caused resentments in many religious communities round the world. Educational systems round the world have had their fair share of damage due to the closures of most schools and universities. This resulted in a decline in learning qualities in spite of the efforts to keep educational systems running though remote internet teaching. All community social outlets such as sports, theater, arts, music and cinema have all come to an almost halt. The

psychological effects of isolations are also significant. Increases in numbers of recorded domestic violence have been observed in many parts of the world [11,12].

Under such dilemma, most governments had to take the difficult decision of lifting or relaxing most of the social distancing measures. This came at the price of a new shoot up in the number of infections. Many countries are now forced to take a second U turn re-imposing some of the restrictions. It seems that the purpose of such ON – OFF policies is to maintain the number of infections under control in such a way that existing health systems do not become overloaded in a way similar to what happened during the first wave. Such ON-OFF policies are likely to continue as long as there is no approved vaccine or treatment for the disease.

It is our purpose here to analyze the world COVID-19 infections and deaths data under the worst scenario assumption of no vaccine and no treatment in the near future

Figure (1) Total number of infections in (a) USA, (b) Spain

(a)

(b)

Daily number of infections in (a) USA, (b) Spain [Data are smoothed with 5 point average]

The Data

All data used in this work are obtained from reference [3]. The data are up to date until October 15, 2020 at least. The site give extensive country by country and the world daily infections, deaths, active cases ...etc. Examples of such individual countries data are presented in figures (1 & 2).

It has been pointed out that individual countries data reflect specific characteristics signatures associated with that particular country. These include the start of the pandemic, effects of environmental conditions if any, health systems

capabilities, government policy regarding social distancing, the degree of adherence of the population to those policies and the date and degree of relaxation of such measures. Consequently, while some countries may show similar time related infections and death numbers, others show different patterns. It is thus difficult to construct a general picture of the situation through the analysis of data for each and every individual country separately. Furthermore, and as far as COVID-19 pandemic is concerned, one must remember that it is a global pandemic and any variation in one particular country must affect most other world countries due to the speed of transportation. Instead, it is much easier to handle the whole inclusive world data, and reach conclusion for the whole globe. The main data used here are those related to the total numbers of infections and the total numbers of deaths worldwide. These data are presented in figure (3)

(a)

(b)

Figure (3) Global COVID-19 data (a) infections (b) Deaths

Figure (3) simply indicate that both infections and death have been on the rise all the time. However, the ratio between number of deaths and number of infections in figure (4) shows an interesting trend. This ratio was between 2 and 4% during the early stages of the pandemic when most infections were within the Wuhan – China region. However, as the pandemic moved to other parts of the world especially Europe, this ratio suffered a dramatic increase reaching over 7% sometime in May 2020. This may have been due to the lack of medical experience and resources to deal with such a new threat. The situation began to change gradually and it currently stands at about 2.8%. This is due to the improvement in medical facilities and the use of several experimental new medication to treat critical cases. There are also unconfirmed claims that the virus has genetic transformations and became less aggressive [13].

Figure (4) Global percentage ratio of the number of deaths to the number of infections caused by COVID-19

Although the cross overall picture presented in figure (3) does not show any trends that the pandemic is showing any encouraging signs of reaching some decline, extrapolation of proper empirical modelling of the pandemic may produce more understanding of the future trend of the pandemic.

Empirical Modelling of the Pandemic

Although the current COVID-19 pandemic has been the most severe compared to other pandemics, it should still follow the same general development behavior pattern of other pandemics. Without any external interventions, any pandemic usually proceed through three main stages.

- 1- The initial onset stage where the number of infections starts and increase relatively slowly.
- 2- The first stage is followed by an exponentially sharp rise in the number of infections.
- 3- The third stage is characterized by the leveling of the number of infections and the pandemic spread is sharply reduced. Such leveling off may come as a result of environmental or weather effects, genetic changes in the virus, or herd immunity gained by the population if the number of infections is high enough.

It can thus be argued that even at the worse moments of the COVID-19 pandemic, the question is not if this pandemic will end but when it will do so. Assuming worst case scenario of no vaccine and no treatment, and that all world population of 7.8 Billion are to be infected, and with the current mortality percentage ratio of 2.8%, this end will come at the super heavy price of over 200 million deaths. This comparable to the 50 million killed by the Spanish flue of 1918 when the world population was only about 1.8 Billion. Even so, the universality of the three stages assumption is still valid. Consequently, the task of modelling the development of any pandemic is reduced to finding the suitable empirical equation which best describes the above three stage, and obtaining the best fitted free parameters which best describes each particular case.

The main differences between one pandemic and another are the speed by which infections increase during the second stage, and the time needed to reach the third stage. The data in figure (3 & 4) show the first two stages mentioned above. However, there seem to be no clear sign of any third stage leveling off so far. The author suggested that such a three stage typical behavior can be mathematically described by a tangent hyperbolic function (*tanh*)^[14]. This function is characterized by all above three properties of initial slow buildup, a followed by sharp rise and an ultimate saturation. Consequently, one can describe the accumulated number of infections or deaths (N) by an empirical equation of the form

$$N = e^{a_1 \tanh\left[\frac{(t-a_2)}{a_3}\right]} + a_4 \quad (1)$$

The exponentiation of the tangent hyperbolic function is introduced for enabling the equation to describe the asymmetry between the start of the rising part and the approach to leveling saturation of the data.

With t being the time in days, a_1 , a_2 , a_3 , and a_4 are free fitting parameters to be determined by the data. These four fitting parameters carry physical significance. The parameter a_1 and a_4 form a direct measure of the total number of infections registered throughout the pandemic when leveling off takes place. This number is equal to $(e^{a_1} - a_4)$. The parameter a_2 determines the amount of horizontal shift on the time axis. The third parameter a_3 governs the speed by which the pandemic is spreading. Such behavior applies to all pandemics including the COVID-19 virus.

This function has an inflection point (hope point) where the curve begins to show some slowdown. The inflection point of equation (1) where its second derivative is equal to zero is given by:

$$X_I = a_3 \tanh^{-1} \left[\frac{(1+a_1^2)^{1/2}-1}{a_1} \right] - a_2 \quad (2)$$

Results and Discussion

To put equation (1) into action, available world data for both infections and casualties are fitted to equation (1) using MATLAB nonlinear fitting facility which only converges if 95% confidence level fit is achieved. The results of such fits and their extrapolations are shown in figure (5). The inflection point is shown as a black circle.

Before attempting to extract any conclusion based on the extrapolated fit in figure (5), and in spite of the technical robustness of the fit, it is necessary to demonstrate that the number of data points included in the fit is sufficient enough, and the inclusion of further future data points would have only minimum effect on the results. It is trivial to say that we simply don't have future data point to carry out this check. Instead, the fits are repeatedly performed using a smaller number of data points by truncating parts of the present available data, and studying the effect such truncation might have on the ultimate results. The idea is to monitor the saturation leveling off and inflection point values using only parts of the available data. The overall available data cover 270 days. Truncations were carried out down to one

month before in steps of 5 days. The results for the inflection point and saturation level obtained in each case for both infections and deaths are presented in table (1). These results indicate that even with about eight months of data, the result are almost the same as those using nine months data. This gives support to the idea that one has already enough number of data points to carry out fits and extrapolations. It is worth mentioning that truncations of more than one month and up to two months produced results that involve about 30% differences from those obtained using the complete data set.

It can thus be reasonably argued that carrying out fits and extrapolations using the currently available data can help in making reasonably acceptable predictions concerning the future evolvement of the pandemic.

Table (1) Comparison of results of fits carried out using different numbers of data points

Infections Fits Analysis Results							
No of Points in the Fit	270	265	260	255	250	245	240
Inflection Point (Days)	283	280	278	278	281	282	285
Saturation (Million)	113	110	108	109	110	112	116
Deaths Fits Analysis Results							
Inflection Point (Days)	175	176	172	167	165	161	158
Saturation (Million)	1.66	1.6	1.57	1.50	1.48	1.41	1.31

Based on the above argument, one may try to predict the future development of the COVID-19 pandemic. It must be emphasized however that the prediction made here are conditional to two constrains. The first is that no approved vaccine or treatment is going to be available in the near or medium future. The second is that

all actions taken by most world countries in confronting the pandemic such as ON and OFF social distancing measures remain generally the same.

(a)

(b)

Figure (5) World COVID-19 data fitted to equation (1). The data are between January 22 and October 16 2020. (a) Infection data. (b) Mortalities data.

With above points in mind, a close look at figure (5) may reveal few interesting points. These are:

- 1- Figure (5-a) indicates that Infections are going to continues throughout 2021 before leveling off.
- 2- The total number of world infections by the end of 2021 may reach 110 ± 10 Million people worldwide before leveling off.
- 3- Number of mortalities caused by the virus may level off much sooner than infections. Figure (5-b) indicate that such leveling off may start 550 days post January 22 2020. This represent sometime in September 2021.
- 4- The accumulated number of deaths before leveling off may reach 1.7 ± 0.4 Million people worldwide. This is in agreement with some WHO estimations.^[15]
- 5- Figure (5) indicates that while the world has passed the inflection point as far as number of death is concerned, infections are just close but have not yet reached this particular point. The importance of this point stems from the fact that it marks the transition from ever increasing new daily infections to decreasing ones.

Although above results are obtained from extrapolating the fits to equation (1), the results concerning the leveling off is consistent with model independent data predictions related to the time needed for the number of infections to double. This time is plotted in figure (6).

Figure (6) Variation of the number of days needed to double the number of world infections at any time

Figure (6) involves few interesting features. The first is the peak near about the end of February 2020 which marked the reduction in the number of infections in Wuhan - China and just before the spread of the virus to other parts of the world. Seventy days post January 22 which is some time near the end of March, total number of infections were doubling every ten days or so. This represents the first wave of the virus spread in Europe and the US. In spite of the fact that total infections have been on the rise ever since, the daily percentage increases have been slowing down. Consequently, the time needed to double the number of infections has been going up. Currently, this figure currently stands at about 180 days and it is on the increase. This mean that the number of infections which currently stands at about 40 Million would double to 80 Million by the end of April 2021 and 160 million by the end of September 2021 provided that the doubling time stays where it stands now. However, and as can be seen from figure (6), this doubling time is on the increase. It is thus not unreasonable to assume that the actual number of infections will be significantly less than 160 Million, and the model extrapolated value of 110 Million may not be far from reality. The same argument holds as far as total number of deaths are concerned.

Conclusions

The model equation suggest is capable of describing both infections and mortality global numbers due to COVID-19 pandemic. Fitted model equation using currently available data produced convergent fits with better than 95% confidence level. Extrapolation of the fitted model leads to estimations of the time ahead before the pandemic reaches the stage of leveling off. According to such extrapolations, such leveling off in infections may not come sooner than some time by the end of 2021 unless some effective vaccine is developed and widely used. The estimated total infections and mortalities by that time are expected to reach 110 and 2 millions respectively.

[1] <https://www.euro.who.int/en/health-topics/health-emergencies/coronavirus-covid19#:~:text=WHO%20announced%20COVID%2D19,on%2011%20March%202020.>

[2] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Herd_immunity

[3] <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/>

[4] Yu Wu, Wenzhan Jing, Jue Liu Qiuyue, Ma JieYuan, Yaping Wang, Min Du, Min Liu. “Effects of temperature and humidity on the daily new cases and new deaths of COVID-19 in 166 countries” *Science of The Total Environment* Volume 729, 10 August 2020, 139051

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.139051>

[5] Yueling Ma, Yadong Zhao, Jiangtao Liu, Xiaotao He, Bo Wang, Shihua Fu, Jun Yan, Jingping Niu, Ji Zhou, Bin Luo “Effects of temperature variation and humidity on the death of COVID-19 in Wuhan, China” *Science of The Total Environment* Volume 724, 1 July 2020, 138226

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138226>

[6] Mugen Ujiie, Shinya Tsuzuki, Norio Ohmagari “Effect of temperature on the infectivity of COVID-19” *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* April 2020

DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2020.04.068>

[7] Ahmet Ozyigit “Understanding Covid-19 transmission: The effect of temperature and health behavior on transmission rates” *Infect Dis Health*. 2020 Jul 8 doi: [10.1016/j.idh.2020.07.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.idh.2020.07.001)

[8] <https://www.nber.org/papers/w27243.pdf>

[9] <https://www.unwomen.org/-/media/headquarters/attachments/sections/library/publications/2020/policy-brief-the-impact-of-covid-19-on-women-en.pdf?la=en&vs=1406>

[10] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Impact_of_the_COVID-19_pandemic_on_aviation

[11] Megan L. Evans, Margo Lindauer, and Maureen E. Farrell. “A Pandemic within a Pandemic — Intimate Partner Violence during Covid-19” *The New England Journal of Medicine* Sep. 16 2020 . DOI: [10.1056/NEJMp2024046](https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMp2024046)

[12] <https://www.webmd.com/lung/news/20200818/radiology-study-suggests-horrifying-rise-in-domestic-violence-during-pandemic>

[13] <https://www.newscientist.com/article/2252699-covid-19-is-becoming-less-deadly-in-europe-but-we-dont-know-why/#:~:text=It%20is%20becoming%20increasingly%20clear,are%20still%20shrouded%20in%20uncertainty>.

[14] Azooz A. A. “Empirical Parametrization of COVID-19 Virus Pandemic “Journal of Multidisciplinary Modeling and Optimization 3(1) (2020), 12-26.

[15] <https://www.reuters.com/article/health-coronavirus-who-briefing-int-idUSKCN26G2TO>